

ONE AGAINST ALL MULTICLASS ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS USING COLORED EDGE DESCRIPTORS

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ABSTRACT

Annotating images automatically is needed for indexing and searching images in a big database. Image annotation can be considered as a multi-class classification problem, where an image may require one or more labels. In this work, One-Against-All (OAA) multi-class ANNs architecture approach is proposed to classifying into multi-class. The extracted features from color and edge descriptors of an image are used as input of the model. Some experiments were performed to achieve the optimal number of hidden neurons of each neural network that can classify its corresponding target successfully. The empirical results outperform multiple label learning approach.

Keywords: Semantic scene classification, Multi-label classification, neural networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

With a lot of documents and pictures that we collect every day, indexing and searching techniques become undoubtedly need to retrieve contents quickly. However, no such system fully satisfies the need of retrieving desired images by users up to now. One approach to retrieve the desired images is that we need to tag all image data we have so that we can use a text-based query against the image data later. Annotating large data should be done automatically, as this task may become cumbersome by hand. Annotation of image content is identified as an important step towards more efficient manipulation and retrieval of images from the image repositories or the Web. There have been many types of research for interpreting the semantic concept of images. However, efficient automatic image annotation is still a very challenging and open problem. One reason is

that it is hard to extract or translate raw pixels into abstract semantics, creating a semantic gap or the mismatches between low-level visual features (e.g. shapes, edges, color) and high-level meaningful entities. To manage this problem, we seek to apply neural networks because artificial neural networks are one of many approaches that can be used to classify and annotate images and it is relatively simple to implement. Artificial Neural Networks can be very useful to create a mapping between input and output while we do not know exactly the relationship between them. Another problem in image annotation is that one image may belong to one or more annotations. By its nature, a classifier can only be used for binary classification problems, so we need to extend it from the underlying structure. One simple approach to do multi-class classification problem is to create a classifier with multi outputs or multi binary classifiers. This study is

attempting to introduce a simple method to perform image annotation by exploring the effectiveness of annotating multi-class images using a system consisting of multiple neural networks. We also performed the comparison between some various parameters in the system, including what features will be utilized as input for neural networks (color feature, edge feature) and what architecture of neural networks will be used.

One way to index images in the huge database is using automatic image labeling. Images may belong to one or more classes, so multi-image classification system is required. In this work, we created a simple model for classifying multi-label images. The proposed model will be developed using several steps which include feature extraction, combining feature vector, and creating multi neural networks. Figure 1 shows the overall architecture of Artificial Neural Network model for the classifier.

2. RELATED WORKS

An image classifier based on unsupervised learning method is proposed for image DE noising and object detection task [8]. A generative deep learning framework is implemented for high resolution image hierarchy using gated Markov random field with the deep belief networks [9]. Based on human object recognition of “initial guess” phenomena, a bilinear deep belief network framework is employed for image annotation where falling into a bad local optimum is avoided [10]. To image tagging and keyword retrieval, a multimodal deep neural network is explored where shared hidden representation of the

neurons is focused [11]. Multi-image annotation has been developed using ANNs [13].

Figure 1. Proposed ANN Architecture

Convolutional neural network architecture used to image annotation for estimating the top ranking [14]. Spatiotemporal features for human robot interaction has been studied using an unsupervised deep learning [15]. A deep convolutional neural network is developed to tackle the task of image super resolution [16]. An SVM-VT model to annotating image is proposed [17]. Minimization of objective functions is done by combining visual features and contextual cues from surrounding tags of an image [18]. When visual content of an image is same, a novel class of kernels can get better results in image annotation task [19]. A combination of PSO and SVM performs satisfactory in the task of image classification and annotation [20]. A seven layer deep neural networks are introduced to tagging of multi-class images [21].

3. TRAINING IN PROCESS

The design of each part in our approach is explained in this section in details. Figure 4 shows the overall process of the proposed multi-class image annotation approach.

A. Dataset

We use the same dataset which is used by the study [6]. It consists of two thousand images belonging to the class trees, sunset, sea, mountains, and desert. Over 22% images contain more than one concept. Table I shows details of the dataset where *d*: desert, *m*: mountains, *s*: sea, *su*: Sunset and *t*: trees. Figure 2 presents sample images with label. To reduce the over fitting problem while building neural networks, we use Five-fold cross-validation. Five pairs of training and testing subset that are generated from random portion 85% and 15% of the data set, respectively. Then, we train and test our model five times using the five-different pair dataset.

TABLE I. THE IMAGE DATABASE

Label	No. of Images	Label	No. of Images
d	340	d+m	19
m	268	d+s	5
s	341	d+su	21
su	216	d+t	20
t	378	m+s	38
m + su	19	d + m + su	1
m + t	106	d + su + t	3
s + su	172	m + s + t	6
s + t	14	m + su + t	1
su + t	28	s + su + t	4

Figure 2. Sample of Training Images with Label

B. Network Architecture

We classify images into multiple classes by creating a system of multiple neural networks one-against-all (OAA, or one-versus-all, or one-versus-rest) [5], where a single classifier is trained per class to distinguish that class from all other classes. Figure 3 presents a k-number of binary neural networks used to classify k object classes. By using this architecture, we may have an advantage regarding scalability that we can add new neural networks trained with new data without disturbing the existing neural networks. In our case, we use a dataset containing five classes, so we train five neural network classifiers, one for each concept, by using the set of labeled training samples provided. All neural networks use the same feature input, which is created by combining Scalable Color Descriptor (256 dimensions), Edge Histogram Descriptor (80 dimensions), and Color Layout Descriptor (12 dimensions), making feature vectors with dimensions of 348 for each image. This following image represents our neural network classifier model.

Each neural network may have a different structure of features to each other. In our case, all the neural networks have the same feature

inputs, some hidden layers, and learning methods using feed-forward structure, one hidden layer, and scaled conjugate back-propagation learning algorithm [6] respectively, but each of them has a different number of hidden layer size. The optimal numbers of hidden neurons must be determined empirically instead of analytically. Per a rule of thumb, the number of neurons in that hidden layer should be between the number of inputs (348 in our case) and the number of outputs (1 in our case). So, in the experiment, we will implement neural networks with various numbers of hidden neurons ranging from 5 to 400.

Figure 3. A K-Number of Binary Neural Networks used to Classify K Object Classes.

C. Feature Extraction

In machine learning, features are discriminative part of an observation object. Choosing the right features is the most important thing in machine learning. If the chosen features are not discriminative, the classifier may not be able to learn pattern among objects observed. So, before designing the structure of a neural network, we should consider what kind of data will be used as input first. We can use either raw pixel image or image feature descriptor as input for a classifier. Egmont et al [1] showed that using feature

extraction have much more advantages and fewer drawbacks than raw pixels. This is because, in addition to lowering computational cost, feature-based approaches are more invariant to noise that make the learning process more robust. However, the chosen features may not be the discriminative or able to represent the relevant information of the original image so we should be careful to choose the various methods of feature extraction. Feature design is one central problem that profoundly influences the outcomes of a machine learning system. Ideally, good features represent an image pattern while having a compact size compared to the designated image at the same time. Image features are specific structures of an image based on its color, shape, texture, etc. It can be represented in different ways. Usually, it is represented as a matrix.

MPEG-7 is a multimedia content description standard. It was standardized in ISO/IEC 15938 (Multimedia content description interface). CLD, SCD, EHD are some of the standard MPEG-7 low-level descriptors and can be generated using Open CV library [2]. The Color Layout Descriptor represents the spatial layout of color images. The Scalable Color Descriptor is a histogram of color in the HSV space. The Edge Histogram Descriptor describes the edges spatial distribution of an image. The input image is divided into 4x4 regions, and for each region, the number of vertical, horizontal, 45-degree, 135-degree, and non-directional edges are calculated. Explanation about color MPEG-7 descriptors can be found in [3], [4]. In our system, we will use these descriptors as input.

Figure 4. Proposed Image Classifier and Training Process

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First, we evaluated some various features as the input of the system and see which one is the best among others. The following Table II. shows accuracy for each model and label. As shown in the table, neural networks with three combined features have always had better results among others, so we can say that in this case, using more features makes a better performance than fewer features. The accuracy is defined as the number of correctly predicted labels over all 300 test images. It is the same as the number on the bottom-right of confusion matrix for each class result. Figure 5 shows the confusion matrix of five-NN with five features on class sunset.

TABLE II. THE ACCURACY COMPARISON AMONG METHODS

Class Name	Method Name			
	3 features	SCD	CLD	EHD
Desert	86.70%	86.30%	82.30%	76.30%
Mountains	87.00%	83.30%	83.00%	80.70%
Sea	74.30%	70.70%	74.30%	72.00%
Sunset	95.00%	92.30%	89.70%	82.70%
Trees	82.30%	81.70%	79.30%	86.70%

Figure 5. Confusion Matrix

TABLE III. THE ACCURACY OF NEURAL NETWORKS WITH DIFFERENT NUMBER OF NEURONS

Class Name	Number of Hidden Neurons				
	65	195	320	325	380
Desert	89.67%	89.27%	89.33%	91.27%	88.40%
Mountains	88.33%	86.27%	89.40%	87.40%	85.87%
Sea	79.20%	79.73%	78.13%	80.20%	80.67%
Sunset	95.23%	96.33%	96.13%	95.80%	91.67%
Trees	90.93%	89.60%	89.87%	89.67%	90.53%

The next experiment aims for looking the best neural networks OAA structure using the best feature input (3 combined features CLD, EHD, and SCD). We implemented 80 neural networks with a different number of hidden neurons ranging from 5 to 400, for each class. Using 5-fold cross validation, we trained and tested each of them with five different pairs of training and testing dataset. The final accuracy of each neural network is calculated from the average of all precision of each dataset.

TABLE IV. MULTI-LABEL CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE OF THE NEURAL NETWORKS

Cycle	Correctly labeled		Partially correct		Incorrectly /no label		Multi-labeled
	#	%	#	%	#	%	
1	18	31.58	30	52.6	9	15.7	57
2	25	38.46	35	53.8	5	7.69	65
3	23	31.94	42	58.3	7	9.72	72
4	25	39.06	35	54.6	4	6.25	64
5	25	39.68	35	55.5	3	4.76	63
Avg.		36.15		55.0		8.84	

As shown in Table II it turned out that the best performing neural networks for class desert, mountains, sea, sunset, are trees are neural networks with the number of hidden neurons 325, 320, 380, 195, and 65, respectively. At this point, we can finalize multiple neural network structure for classifying images. We used these optimal number of hidden neurons obtained in the class for the corresponding neural network, and all the neural networks (each of which classifying different labels) output will be combined to annotate multi-label images. Table III details the accuracy of neural networks with different number of neurons.

TABLE V. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON AMONG OTHER METHOD

Approach	Performance metrics	
	One-error	Average Precision
<i>Proposed method (OAA Neural Networks)</i>	<i>.160 ± .012</i>	<i>.892 ± .010</i>
MIML-Boost	.351 ± .039	.777 ± .025
ADA-Boost.MH	.451 ± .046	.708 ± .030
MLSVM	.327 ± .033	.783 ± .020
MIMLSVM	.368 ± .032	.756 ± .022

Figure 6. Image Annotation Result

Results in the multi-label problem are somewhat different from results in single-label classification, as some images may have all correct labels, partially correct labels, or may not have any right label at all, as shown in Figure 6. After doing five iterations, we got overall 36% of multi-labeled images that have all correct labels, 55% of images with partially correct labels, and 8% of images with no correct label which all are shown in Table IV. To make our results of multi-label annotation comparable to other methods, we used a performance evaluation method [7]. The average precision definition here is different from the precision definition for classic single-label classification, as described in [9] because the result in multi-label classification can be entirely incorrect, partially correct, or fully correct. Also, we compared our work performance with MIML-Boost, ADA-Boost.MH, MLSVM, and MIMLSVM proposed by [8]. As shown in the Table V, we find that by tuning parameters of NN, multiple neural networks can make better results than multi-instance multi-label learning methods.

5. CONCLUSION

Here we proposed a simple and intuitive approach to coping multi-label image classification problem, where one image may contain one or more labels. Starting a simple method is important to identify our system drawbacks faster so we can make the next

decision to come up with the next more sophisticated methods more quickly. We used some of the MPEG-7 feature descriptors as feature input for neural networks and tried some variations of OAA classifier structure. It turned out that using more features generally makes better results than using less features. Besides, an architecture containing multiple neural networks with single output can be optimized by using a different architecture for each neural network, such as varying the number of hidden neurons. This architecture seems promising as its performance outperforms some other more sophisticated approaches for multi-label classification problem.

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